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METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR ESTIMATION OF ATOMOXETINE HCl BY USING RP-HPLC IN BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid and sensitive RP-HPLC method was developed by trail and error and validated for estimation of Atomoxetine HCl in bulk and tablet dosage form. Chromatography was carried out by using pre packed Luna C18,μ(250 x 4.6mm) phenomenex column as a stationary phase with mobile phase containing a mixture of 0.1% Triethylamine (pH-3.5)adjusted with OPA:acetonitrile in the ratio of 50:50v/v. The flow rate was 1ml/min. The effluent was monitored at 271nm and retention time of drug is 3.0mins. calibraton curve was plotted with the range of 2-12μg/ml for atomoxetine HCl and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999. The percentage values for all the parameters was found to be not more than 2 for RP-HPLC . Validation studies revealed that method is specific, rapid, reliable and reproducible. The high recovery and low relative standard deviation and relative standard deviation confirm the suitability of the method for routine determination of Atomoxetine HCl in bulk and tablet dosage form. The developed method used for routine analysis of Atomoxetine HCl in pharmaceutical dosage form and method is developed and validated as per ICH guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION

Atomoxetine HCl is an anti-depressant drug, it is official in Indian Pharmacopoeia and is a one of the selective nor-adrenaline reuptake inhibitors. Atomoxetine is the only the salt form, from its classification and it is used for the treatment of attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder(ADHD).Atomoxetine is Chemically (R)-N-methyl-(O-tolyoxy)-propylamine hydrochloride and its empirical formula of Atomoxetine HCl is $C_{17}H_{21}NO.HCL$ having a molecular weight of 291.82.

Literature survey reveals few chromatographic method i.e., HPLC, HTPLC, visible methods for estimation of Atomoxetine HCl in pharmaceutical dosage form and spectroscopic method like Uv-spectrophotometric, the present study describes a new quantitative method development by using RP-HPLC. The purpose of developing and validating a method should be a simple, rapid, sensitive, precise, and accurate. The method was optimised with low retention time and run time for this method so, the consumption of mobile phase is less which makes the method economical and rapid. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines and can be used for routine analysis.^[1-7]The main objective is to develop a simple, accurate and precise, more sensitive, cost effective method and can be used for routine analysis

MATERIALS AND MATERIALS

Chemicals And Reagents:

Pure drug sample of Atomoxetine HCl was obtained from Tokyo chemical industry co., LTD. And tablet formulation (AXEPTA) was purchased from Shabbir medical hall, Hyderabad, India, with label claim of 25mg.

Acetonitrile, methanol, HPLC grade water, triethylamine was procured from SD-Fine Chem-Limited and orthophosphoric acid was procured from MERCK.

Instrumentation:

The analysis was performed by using Shimadzu 20AD RP-HPLC instrument with Phenomenex Luna C18 column (250 x 4.6mm) 5 μ m, It contains Rhenodyne valve with 20 μ l fixed loop injector with UV -Visible detector. and UV-Visible spectrophotometry instrument i.e., Elico 210 with spectra treats software, analytical balance (Contech)are used for weighing, pH(Elico),Sonicator(labotech)was used for degassing the mobile phase, were used during the study.

Chromatographic Condition:

RP-HPLC analysis was carried out on C18 (Phenomenex, 250 x 4.6mm, particle size 5 μ m)with reversed phase column. The mobile phase consist of a mixture of acetonitrile:0.1% triethylamine at pH-3.5(adjusted with OPA) (50:50V/v).The flow rate of mobile phase was 1ml/min with isocratic elution. the injection volume 20 μ l and run time was 10 mins. The detection was carried out at 271nm.

Preparation Of 0.1% Triethylamine (pH-3.5):

Measured accurately 0.1ml triethylamine and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask and to that add 100ml of HPLC grade water and adjust the pH-3.5 by using orthophosphoric acid. filtered through 0.45 μ membrane filter.

Preparation Of Mobile Phase:

Add 50ml of 0.1% triethylamine buffer pH-3.5 to 50ml of acetonitrile and degas it.

Preparation Of Atomoxetine HCl Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weighed and transferred 100mg of atomoxetine HCl into 100ml volumetric flask, to that mixture add 50ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve. and then make up to the mark by using diluent(i.e.,1000 μ g/ml). Pipette out 1ml from 1000 μ g/ml into 10ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with diluent i.e., 100 μ g/ml.

Preparation Of Sample Solution:

Accurately weighed 10 tablets and average weight was calculated. accurately weighed and transferred the sample equivalent to 100mg of atomoxetine HCl into 100ml volumetric flask. To this add 5ml of diluent and sonicated to dissolve it completely and make up to the mark with diluent. further pipette out 1ml of above solution into 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with the same solvent.

Selection Of Analytical Wavelength:

10 μ g/ml solution was scanned in the wavelength range of 200-400nm in order to observe maximum absorbance. the λ_{max} for Atomoxetine HCl is 271nm,since It shows maximum absorbance at that λ_{max} .

Optimisation of proposed method.

Trail -1:

- Diluent** : Mobile phase
- Column** : C18 phenomenex
- Mobile phase** : (pH-5) phosphate buffer :methanol(40:60)
- Injection volume** : 20ul
- Flow rate** : 1.0ml/min
- Detection wavelength** : 271nm

Fig 1: Chromatogram of trail-1.

Name	R _T	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCl	9.065	806809	3442.813	3.375	12.552
	10.623	2608	935.985		

Trial -2:

- Diluent** : Mobile phase
- Column** : C18 phenomenex
- Mobile phase** : (pH-5) phosphate buffer :methanol(30:70)
- Injection volume** : 20ul
- Flow rate** : 1.0ml/mL
- Detection wavelength** : 271nm

Fig 2 :Chromatogram of trail-2.

Name	R _T	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCl	4.932	661851	2751.2	3.246	5.20
	5.825	118154	499.13		

Trail -3:

Diluent : Mobile phase
Column : C18 Phenomenex
Mobile phase : (pH4) 0.1% Ortho phosphoric acid :acetonitrile (40:60)
Injection Volume : 20 μ l
Flow rate : 1.0ml/min
Detection wavelength : 271nm

Fig 3: Chromatogram of trail-3.

Name	R _T	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCl	5.136	3363747	2342.546	2.224	7.223

Trail-4:

Diluent : Mobile phase
Column : Phenomenex (250 x 4.5mm) 5 μ
Mobile phase : (pH 3.5)0.1% triethylamine : Acetonitrile (60:40)
Injection Volume : 20 μ l
Flow rate : 1.0 ml/ min
Detection wavelength : 271nm.

Fig 4 :Chromatogram of trail-4.

Name	R _T	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCl	5.705	64956	2371.788	0.823	9.143

Trail -5:

Diluent : Mobile phase
Column : Phenomenex (250 x 4.5mm) 5 μ
Mobile phase : (pH 3.5)0.1%Triethylamine : Acetonitrile (55:45)
Injection Volume : 20 μ l
Flow rate : 1.0 ml/ min
Detection wavelength : 271nm

Fig 5 : Chromatogram of trail-5.

Name	R _T	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCL	4.177	61413	2594.474	0.775	6.132

Conclusion:

Trail-1: The peak shape is asymmetrical , retention time is more, tailing factor is more than 2 so it is not satisfactory

Trail-2: The peak shape is asymmetrical and tailing factor is more.

Trail-3: The tailing factor is more than 2.

Trail-4: Here drug peak is asymmetrical and retention time is high

Trail-5: Here drug peak is fronting in shape and retention is more

Trail-6: optimised method

Optimised method:

Diluent : Mobile phase
Column : Phenomenex (250 x 4.6mm) 5 μ
Mobile phase : (pH-3.5) 0.1% triethylamine : Acetonitrile (50:50)
Injection Volume : 20 μ l
Flow rate : 1.0 ml/ min
Detection wavelength : 271nm

Fig 6: Chromatogram of trail-6.

Name	RT	Area	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Resolution
Atomoxetine HCl	3.022	51445	3961.164	1.527	5.159

Conclusion: peak shape is symmetrical and retention is less and all the parameters are with the limits

Method Validation:^[8-9]

Both RP-HPLC and UV methods were developed and validated by using following parameters such as linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, LOD, LOQ.

System Suitability:

In HPLC, it is an integral part of method development used to ensure the performance of HPLC system. The parameters such as retention time (R_t), number of theoretical plates (N), and tailing factor (T) were evaluated for six Replicates injections at a concentration of 10 μ g/ml.

Linearity:

Linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte in the sample.

Accuracy:

It is the measure of the closeness of the experimental value is to the true value. Accuracy should be established across the specified range of the analytical procedure.

Intraday Precision:

It expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time.

Inter Day Precision:

It expresses the precision between laboratories variations, different days, different analysts, different equipment etc.

Limit Of Detection:

It is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample which can be detected, but not necessarily quantified, as an exact value under the stated

Limit Of Quantification:

It is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample which can be detected and quantified.

Robustness:

It is a measure of the method capability to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Results of HPLC:****System Suitability:**

The six replicates of injections at a concentration of 10 μ g/ml were prepared separately and injected and all the parameters were calculated.

Table -1: Results Of System Suitability.

S.NO	RT	AREA	THEORITICAL PLATE	TAILING FACTOR	RESOLUTION
1	3.084	50664	3698.78	1.450	5.6
2	3.077	50836	327.97	1.352	5.5
3	3.087	50248	3823.78	1.258	5.0
4	3.047	50699	4198.19	1.382	5.2
5	3.020	50818	4733.27	1.212	5.3
6	3.032	51322	4135.97	1.234	5.2
MEAN	3.057	50764.5	3415.8	1.314	5.3
SD	0.026	316.21			
%RSD	0.8%	0.6%			

Specificity:**Fig-8: Chromatogram Of Standard 10 μ g/ml.**

Fig -9: Chromatogram Of Sample 10µg/ml.

Linearity:

The linearity was determined using primary standard solution, to establish linearity following concentration range of 2,4,6,8,10,12µg/ml.

Table-2:Results Of Linearity.

CONC	RT	PEAK AREA
2µg/ml	3.035	11129
4 µg/ml	3.008	21101
6 µg/ml	3.031	30340
8 µg/ml	3.008	41657
10 µg/ml	3.022	51445
12 µg/ml	3.085	60746

Fig -10: Linearity Graph Of HPLC.

Accuracy:

The accuracy was developed by recovery studies which were carried out at three different spiked levels i.e., 80%,100%,120%

Table-3:Results Of Accuracy.

SAMPLE ID	CONC($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		TOTAL CONC	AREA	% RECOVERY	AVG% RECOVERY	SD	%RSD
	Amount of pure drug	Amount of sample						
80%	4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	46077	99.6%	99.76%	89.6	0.2%
80%	4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		46249	100.1%			
80%	4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		46045	99.6%			
100%	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	50636	99.6%	99.23%	342.2	0.7%
100%	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		50409	98.2%			
100%	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		51228	99.9%			
120%	6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	11 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	56303	99.0%	99.43%	184.3	0.3%
120%	6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		55291	99.6%			
120%	6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		55906	99.7%			

Precision:

Table -4 Intraday Precision.

S.NO	RETENTION TIME	AREA	%ASSAY
1	3.023	51223	100.2%
2	3.048	51522	100.8%
3	3.051	51510	100.8%
4	3.057	51349	100.5%
5	3.025	51225	100.2%
6	3.027	51207	100.2%5
MEAN	3.038	51339.3	-
SD	0.013	133.35	-
%RSD	0.42%	0.25%	-

Table -5 Inter Day Precision.

S.NO	RETENTION TIME	AREA	%ASSAY
1	3.077	51546	100.9%
2	3.084	51789	101.4%
3	3.019	51408	100.6%
4	3.028	51904	101.6%
5	3.057	51343	100.5%
6	3.039	51434	100.6%
MEAN	3.050	51570.6	-
SD	0.02	206.7	-
%RSD	0.65%	0.4%	-

Robustness :Change in flow rate($\pm 0.1/\text{min}$)

Table – 6: Results Of Change In Flow Rate.

S.NO	1.1ml/min			0.9ml/min		
	RT	AREA	% ASSAY	RT	AREA	%ASSAY
1	2.915	50665	99.1%	3.133	50555	98.9%
2	2.917	50647	99.1%	3.193	50227	98.2%
3	2.905	50781	99.3%	3.175	50818	99.4%
MEAN	2.912	50597.66	-	3.167	50533.33	-
SD	0.0051	59.38	-	0.021	418.74	-
%RSD	0.1%	0.1%	-	0.6%	0.8%	-

Change in mobile phase(± 2)

Table -7 : Results Of Change In Mobile Phase.

S.NO	52:48			48:52		
	RT	AREA	% ASSAY	RT	AREA	%ASSAY
1	2.946	50211	98.2%	3.169	50583	98.9%
2	2.911	50935	99.6%	3.157	50605	99.03%
3	2.973	50141	98.1%	3.126	50856	99.5%
MEAN	2.943	50429	-	3.150	50681.3	-
SD	0.019	358.93	-	0.018	123.83	-
%RSD	0.6%	0.7%	-	0.5%	0.2%	-

Change in pH(± 0.2)

Table – 8:Results Of Change In Ph.

S.NO	pH (3.3)			pH(3.7)		
	RT	AREA	% ASSAY	RT	AREA	%ASSAY
1	2.904	50463	98.7%	3.165	50714	99.2%
2	2.953	50788	99.4%	3.164	50984	99.7%
3	2.915	50228	98.2%	3.166	50357	98.5%
MEAN	2.924	50429	-	3.165	50685	-
SD	0.02	358.93	-	0.00081	256.79	-
%RSD	0.6%	0.7%	-	0.02%	0.5%	-

LOD & LOQ:

Table -9: Results Of LOD & LOQ.

PARAMETERS	SLOPE	INTERCEPT	LOD	LOQ
1	5006	1026	$3.3 \times \sigma/S=$	$10 \times \sigma/S=$
2	4962	1143	$3.3 \times 49.6/4977.3 = 0.03 \mu\text{g/ml}$	$10 \times 49.6/4977.3$
3	4964	1113		$= 0.09 \mu\text{g/ml}$
MEAN	4977.3	1094		
SD		49.6		

Assay Of Marketed Formulation:

Table-10: Results Of Assay.

DRUG	CONCENTRATION($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	AMOUNT FOUND	%ASSAY
Atomoxetine HCl(25mg)	10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10.08mg	100.8%

CONCLUSION

The method was successfully developed for estimation of Atomoxetine HCl in pharmaceutical dosage form by using RP-HPLC and the validation parameters results have proved that the method is selective, precise, accurate, linear.

The developed method was validated as per the International Conference On Harmonization ICH(Q2B) guidelines, and was found to be applicable for routine quantitative analysis of Atomoxetine HCl by RP-HPLC in tablet dosage forms.

This method is more sensitive than previously reported methods, due to its high sensitivity. hence above method can be used in quality control for routine analysis of tablets of Atomoxetine HCl without any interferences.

We can extend this work by performing simultaneous method and degradation studies i.e., stability studies. We can still reduce the retention time. With high sensitive instrument we can reduce concentration to ngs. Even LC-MS analysis can also be done with same buffer since the buffer is suitable for LC-MS.

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